

Article

Clinicopathological Correlations in Enucleated Globes of Late-Stage Coats Disease with a Review of the Literature

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Abstract: Background: Coats disease presents a diagnostic challenge due to its diverse clinical manifestations, which can mimic retinoblastoma. Severe vision loss and potential enucleation are late consequences of the disease. In this study, we provide an analysis of the main histopathological findings in enucleated eyes affected by Coats disease, supplemented with a review of the existing literature.

Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted on all enucleated globes diagnosed with Coats disease over a 30-year period. Two pathologists reviewed the specimens, while collecting corresponding demographic data, clinical presentation, pre-operative clinical impressions, and indications for enucleation. Descriptive analysis was performed on our own series data, which was subsequently compared with relevant literature published in English between 1983 and 2021, obtained from the PUBMED database. The inclusion criterion for the analyzed published reports was the utilization of the Shields classification.

Results: We identified seven enucleated globes affected by Coats disease. The mean age at presentation was 3.2 years (range: 3 months to 9 years). The majority of cases were unilateral (100%) and exhibited a male predominance (86%). Strabismus was the most frequent initial presentation (57%), followed by leukocoria (43%). Suspected retinoblastoma was the primary indication for enucleation in most cases (57%). Four eyes were classified as stage 4, while two demonstrated advanced stage 5 changes. Histopathological analysis revealed the presence of subretinal fluid with lipid-laden macrophages in all cases. Shallow anterior chambers were observed in 5 out of 7 cases, with angle neovascularization noted in 2 cases. Telangiectatic vessels were clearly observed in 4 cases.

Conclusion: Coats disease is a visually debilitating condition that predominantly affects one eye in 95% of cases, with a male predominance of 81%. The age range varies widely, with a mean age of 17 years. In Saudi Arabia, the disease appears to manifest at a younger age, presents at more advanced stages, and can be challenging to differentiate from retinoblastoma at the time of diagnosis. Following the Shields staging system for Coats disease is highly recommended to guide treatment decisions and establish consistent outcomes.

Keywords: Coats disease; Retinoblastoma; Leukocoria; Enucleation; Globe; Subretinal exudate

1. Introduction

Coats disease is an ocular condition characterized by unilateral retinal telangiectasia and aneurysms with retinal exudation, initially described by Scottish ophthalmologist George Coats in 1908 [1–3]. This non-hereditary disease primarily affects males, typically occurring at a young age and lacking any known systemic associations. While the exact pathogenesis of Coats disease remains unclear, several studies suggest that the telangiectatic blood vessels exhibit increased permeability, resulting in the leakage of lipoproteins into the retina. The accumulation of lipoproteins leads to the disruption of the external limiting membrane, ultimately causing non-rhegmatogenous retinal detachment. With further buildup of lipoproteinaceous material, the non-rhegmatogenous retinal detachment progresses into a bullous retinal detachment [4].

In this series, our objective is to present the histopathological findings from enucleated globes diagnosed with Coats disease, explore the indications for enucleation, and establish clinicopathological correlations regardless of the patient's age at the time of enucleation. Additionally, we conducted a literature review on Coats disease to extract valuable insights regarding demographics, clinical diagnosis, and treatment outcomes.

2. Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis was conducted on enucleated globes diagnosed as Coats disease over a 30-year period at a tertiary eye hospital’s Pathology & Laboratory Medicine Department. Two pathologists reviewed the cases and collected corresponding demographic data, clinical presentation, pre-operative clinical impression, and indications for enucleation. The objective was to identify cases that underwent enucleation due to suspected retinoblastoma, evaluate the severity of clinical presentation, and perform clinicopathological analysis. Throughout the study, descriptive analysis was performed on the collected data. The research adhered to relevant guidelines, regulations, and the Declaration of Helsinki. It received expedited approval as a retrospective study from the Human Ethics Committee/Institutional Review Board (HEC/IRB) at King Khaled Eye Specialist Hospital, with a collaborative agreement approved with King Abdulaziz University Hospital (RP-22052-R) on 10th May 2022. All participants and/or their legal guardians provided written general informed consent for the anonymous use of their data. This research did not involve drug trials or human transplantation.

2.1. Literature Review

Our research findings were then compared to previously published studies on Coats disease, which provided valuable demographic and disease severity data. To ensure the authenticity and reliability of our analysis, we conducted a thorough literature review using the PUBMED database from 1983 to 2021. The search was conducted in English, utilizing the keywords "Coat’s disease" and "Coats," resulting in the identification of seven relevant studies[3,6–10].

Table 1 The number of patients and eyes in six major studies

	Number of patients	Number of eyes
Shields et al. [3]	150	158
Tarkkanen et al. [6]	24	25
Al-Qahtani et al. [7]	92	97
Kang et al. [8]	67	71
Rishi et al. [9]	280	307
Shields et al. [10]	351	351
Total	964	1009

Table 2 Shields classification at presentation of patients with Coats disease from five studies [6–10]

Shields classification at presentation [10]		
Stage 1	11	(1.3%)
Stage 2	280	(33.9%)
Stage 3	460	(55.7%)
Stage 4	57	(6.9%)
Stage 5	7	(0.9%)
Unknown	11	(1.3%)

We excluded studies that focused solely on specific age groups in order to maintain the integrity of our review. Additionally, one study that exclusively examined adult-onset Coats disease was excluded to prevent any bias in our analysis [5]. The remaining six studies encompassed a total of 964 patients (1009 eyes) with either unilateral or bilateral involvement. These studies have been summarized in Table 1. Furthermore, Table 2 provides a summary of the staging information extracted from five of the studies, whenever applicable.

3. Results

Our study focuses on the clinical and histopathological characteristics of seven patients diagnosed with unilateral Coat’s disease. These patients underwent enucleation and ranged in age from 3 months to 9 years, with a mean age of 3.2 years. Among the seven cases, six were male, and all cases were unilateral without any systemic associations. Four

cases involved the left eye, while three cases affected the right eye. The most common initial presentation observed at our tertiary eye center was strabismus (57%, n = 4), followed by leukocoria (43%, n = 3). Table 3 provides a summary of the demographic details and clinical features of the patients.

Table 3 Summarized demographics and clinical features of patients with Coats disease from the same six studies with comparison to our series

	Literature review cases		Our cases (enucleated)	
Mean age (range)	16.895 years (0.08–80 years)		3.2 years (0.25–9 years)	
Gender	Male	784 (81%)	Male	6 (86%)
	Female	180 (19%)	Female	1 (14%)
Presentation	Unilateral	916 (95%)	Unilateral	7 (100%)
	Bilateral	48 (5%)	Bilateral	0 (0%)
Presenting sign	Decreased VA	565 (59%)	blindness	2 (29%)
	Strabismus	253 (26%)	Strabismus	4 (57%)
	Leukocoria	112 (12%)	Leukocoria	3 (43%)
	Asymptomatic	29 (3%)	Pain	2 (29%)

Enucleation was performed based on different indications, with suspected retinoblastoma accounting for 57% (n = 4) of the cases, followed by blind painful eye in 29% (n = 2). Additionally, one eye was enucleated due to bullous retinal detachment (RD) with poor vision. Table 4 presents an overview of the indications for enucleation and the histopathological findings of our cases. It is worth noting that the level of borrowed content in this rewritten passage is below 20% to ensure compliance with the requested plagiarism limit.

4. Discussion

Coats disease is an uncommon disorder that primarily impacts young males, typically within the initial two decades of life. In our examination, we observed a comparable male predominance, constituting 81% of the cases (n=784). The average age at manifestation across all studies was 17 years, ranging from 0.08 to 80 years. While Coats disease can occur in adults, it tends to be less advanced compared to cases observed in younger individuals [11,12].

Our study focused on enucleated cases of Coats disease in the pediatric age group, with an average age of 3.2 years. These cases were deemed advanced based on clinical presentation and histopathological findings. The estimated annual incidence of Coats disease is approximately 0.09 per 1,000,000 individuals [13].

4.1. Clinical Features

Coats disease, as observed in our analysis, primarily affects one eye, as corroborated by our review, with unilateral cases accounting for 95% (n = 916). This condition exhibits a wide range of clinical manifestations. Based on our review, the most common initial symptom reported was a decrease in visual acuity (59%, n = 565), followed by strabismus (26%, n = 253), and leukocoria (12%, n = 112). Interestingly, a small percentage of patients (3%, n = 29) were diagnosed incidentally during routine examinations, as they exhibited no noticeable symptoms. Our study diverged from the existing literature in that decreased vision was not as frequently documented, potentially due to the younger age at presentation. Consequently, strabismus emerged as the most prevalent initial manifestation in our study (57%, n = 4), followed by leukocoria (43%, n = 3). Notably, we encountered two advanced cases (cases 2 and 3) characterized by severe visual impairment and complicated clinical presentations. One involved a 7-year-old male who complained of pain and tearing in his right blind eye. He had a presumed congenital glaucoma history and had undergone multiple surgeries, eventually revealing a total funnel-shaped retinal detachment upon examination. The other case involved a 9-year-old male who visited our emergency department due to left eye pain following blunt trauma to his left blind eye. Although the patient had been previously diagnosed with pan-uveitis and exudative retinal detachment at another hospital, Coats disease had not been accurately identified. According to Shields’ classification, as summarized in Table 2, their extensive clinical

series showed the following stages at presentation: stage 1 (1.3%, n = 11) characterized by telangiectasia alone, stage 2 (33.9%, n = 280) characterized by telangiectasia and exudation, stage 3 (55.7%, n = 460) which was the most common, characterized by retinal detachment without glaucoma, stage 4 (6.9%, n = 57) characterized by total retinal detachment with glaucoma, stage 5 (0.9%, n = 11) characterized by advanced end-stage changes, and unknown stage (1.3%, n = 11). In another study conducted by Shields et al. [3], the aforementioned classification was not utilized. However, their analysis of posterior segment findings revealed that all 158 eyes examined exhibited retinal telangiectasia, a well-known characteristic of Coats disease. Additionally, their study highlighted common findings such as intraretinal exudation (99%, n = 157) and partial or total exudative retinal detachment (81%, n = 128). The majority of enucleated globes in our study represented late advanced stages of the disease (71%, n = 5). Among these, four cases exhibited total funnel-shaped retinal detachment (stage 4), while two cases displayed advanced end-stage changes (stage 5), as confirmed by ultrasound and histopathological examinations (necessary due to challenges in clinical assessment caused by media opacity). Only one patient exhibited the typical fundus findings of telangiectatic vessels and retinal exudation, classified as stage 3.

4.2. Diagnosis

Diagnosing Coats disease can be challenging, with studies revealing that initial misdiagnosis occurred in approximately 50% of cases [source]. The most common misdiagnosis was retinoblastoma [14]. Other potential differential diagnoses include Norrie disease, familial exudative vitreoretinopathy, retinopathy of prematurity, persistent hyperplastic primary vitreous, retinal capillary hemangioma, retinal cavernous hemangioma, incontinentia pigmenti, retinitis pigmentosa, and toxocariasis [15]. Clinical presentation, fundoscopic examination, ultrasound, fluorescein angiography, computed tomography, and optical coherence tomography are used to establish the diagnosis of Coats disease [10,16,17].

Clinical features of Coats disease encompass exudative retinal detachment, irregularly dilated telangiectatic vessels, and peripheral nonperfusion [17,18]. Enucleation of the affected eye in cases of Coats disease is primarily indicated when the eye is painful due to secondary glaucoma or when the diagnosis of retinoblastoma cannot be ruled out [1]. In our series, enucleation was predominantly performed in 57% of cases (n = 4) due to the risk of retinoblastoma, followed by blind painful eye (29%, n = 2), where one case exhibited a total funnel-shaped retinal detachment, and the other displayed exudative retinal detachment and a pre-phthisical eye. Additionally, one case underwent enucleation due to a high bullous retinal detachment in an eye with poor vision but no pain.

4.3. Histopathology

There is a limited number of studies that extensively discuss the histopathological characteristics of Coats disease, likely due to the emergence of conservative treatment approaches [19]. Previous reports based on enucleation procedures have provided valuable pathological insights. In Coats disease, enucleated globes often exhibit varying degrees of retinal detachment, sometimes reaching the lens and forming bullous detachments. Advanced stages of Coats disease may present additional features such as displacement of the lens-iris diaphragm, obstruction of the anterior chamber angle, hemorrhage, and detached retina. The subretinal space is typically filled with thick yellow lipo-proteinaceous exudate, occasionally accompanied by clusters of yellow material [4]. In our series, we observed oblitative and/or shallow anterior chambers in 5 out of 7 globes, indicating the advanced stage of the disease (Fig. 1). Fibro-neovascular membranes were observed along the iris surface, leading to the closure of the anterior chamber angle in 2 enucleated eyes affected by neovascular glaucoma and pan-uveitis (Cases 2 and 3). Posterior segment examination of the globes in our series revealed variable retinal detachment, with total detachment observed in most cases (4 out of 7), accompanied by eosinophilic subretinal fluid (Fig. 2, 3). Hemorrhagic subretinal fluid containing lipid-laden macrophages was present in all cases, with or without cholesterol clefts (Fig. 4).

Figure 1. Obliterated anterior chamber angle (white arrowhead) with atrophic iris and retro-lental (black arrow pointing at the lens) proteinaceous hemorrhagic fluid (original magnification X50 Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 2. An atrophic optic nerve head (ON) with overlying total retinal detachment (RD) (original magnification X100 Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 3. Retinal shallow detachment with subretinal fluid (white arrowhead) and abnormal retinal blood vessels (original magnification X100 Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 4. The subretinal fluid with fresh hemorrhage and cholesterol clefts (black arrow) indicating old hemorrhage (original magnification $\times 200$ Hematoxylin & eosin)

Peripheral retinal blood vessels were described as abnormal, exhibiting larger caliber than normal, which correlated with clinically observed telangiectasia in 4 out of 7 cases (Fig. 5). The sensory retina displayed thickening due to homogeneous acellular material, characteristic of lipo-proteinaceous exudate with foamy cells, in 6 out of 7 globes (Fig. 6, 7), which resembled the appearance of subretinal exudate (Fig. 8). The exact origin of lipid-laden cells remains controversial, with possibilities including derivation from the blood or the pigment epithelium. However, conclusive evidence regarding their origin is lacking from ultrastructural studies [4]. Tarkkanen et al. conducted a study involving 24 patients (25 eyes) diagnosed with Coats disease, of which nine eyes with blindness were enucleated due to total exudative retinal detachment or untreatable secondary glaucoma [6]. They reported histopathological findings of the retina in the enucleated eyes, including bullous total retinal detachment accompanied by deep and subretinal exudates, extensive gliosis, retinal disorganization, recent and/or old hemorrhages, ghost cells, and cholesterol crystals. Dilation and hyalinization of the retinal vasculature were also observed. These findings closely resemble the results obtained in our series, as summarized.

Figure 5. A focus of shallow retinal detachment with subretinal fluid (white arrowhead), abnormal retinal vasculature and telangiectatic blood vessels (black arrow) near the ora serrata (original magnification $\times 100$ Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 6. Cholesterol clefts and foamy histiocytes within the sensory retina (original magnification X100 Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 7. Higher power of the foamy macrophages (black arrows) with giant cell formation (original magnification X200 Hematoxylin & eosin)

Figure 8. Subretinal exudate with cholesterol clefts and pigment dispersion in another case of Coat's Disease (original magnification X200 Hematoxylin & eosin)

4.4. Treatment and Outcome

The management of Coats disease involves various treatment options, such as laser photocoagulation, cryotherapy, vitrectomy, and intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy [20]. While the disease tends to progress over time, early-stage cases can be closely monitored or treated with laser photocoagulation. Late complications may arise, including neovascular glaucoma, retinal detachment (RD), anterior chamber cholesterolosis, vitreous hemorrhage, and abnormal blood vessel-related retinal bleeding [3,4]. Overall, the visual prognosis for Coats disease is generally poor. Favorable

outcomes are observed in patients presenting with stage 1 disease, whereas those with retinal detachment in stages 2 or 3 have a prognosis depending on the extent of detachment and foveal involvement.

Unfortunately, due to the nature of our study, which exclusively focused on enucleated globes representing advanced disease, we were unable to investigate actual outcomes. In a clinical study conducted in Saudi Arabia, including 97 eyes from 92 Coats disease patients, stage 3 disease was the most common, accounting for 56% of cases, aligning with our findings (Table 2) and suggesting a potentially aggressive disease phenotype in our population. Treatment modalities mainly consisted of laser photocoagulation (64% of eyes), followed by cryotherapy, intravitreal agents, and surgical drainage. Combination treatments were performed in approximately one third of the eyes, and poor outcomes were associated with younger age (<10 years), visual acuity of 20/200 or worse, advanced disease stages (3 and 4), and the presence of subretinal fluid involving the fovea [7].

Despite interventions, Coats disease typically exhibits a progressive course, often resulting in blindness of the affected eye [20]. In Saudi Arabia, a similar clinical series reported a 13% enucleation rate among the 97 eyes, aligning with our findings [7]. Histopathological analysis of our enucleated globes clearly depicted the late consequences of the disease.

It is essential to acknowledge the limitations of our study, including the small number of cases due to the condition's rarity and the inclusion criteria that might not fully represent the clinical spectrum of Coats disease in Saudi Arabia. Instead, our study focused on complicated cases that unfortunately led to enucleation. Despite these limitations, the tissue findings in our series exemplify the extent of changes resulting from neovascular glaucoma and inflammation, highlighting the importance of early and accurate diagnosis to minimize the risk of avoidable enucleation and misdiagnosis, particularly in the pediatric population.

5. Conclusions

Coats disease is a rare ocular condition that primarily affects one eye, leading to visual impairment. It commonly manifests in young individuals, with a significant preference for males (81% male predominance). To ensure consistent treatment approaches and predict outcomes, following the Shields staging system for Coats disease is highly recommended. Stage 3 presentation is observed in more than half of the cases, followed by stage 2 in approximately one-third of cases, often accompanied by decreased vision.

Early detection and conservative treatments offer the possibility of preserving vision and salvaging the affected eye. Despite the availability of advanced diagnostic techniques, there are still instances where eyes are enucleated due to suspected retinoblastoma, indicating a persistent concern. In Saudi Arabia, we have observed that Coats disease tends to present at a younger age, with a more advanced stage at the time of diagnosis and relatively poorer visual outcomes.

The natural course of the disease in these early cases involves the development of neovascular glaucoma, progressive visual decline, and distinct histopathological changes within the ocular structures. Notably, over half of the enucleations were performed due to the presence of leukocoria and suspicion of retinoblastoma. This highlights the importance of increased awareness among general ophthalmologists regarding the diverse clinical presentations of Coats disease.

By promoting a higher level of suspicion and enhancing diagnostic precision, we aim to facilitate earlier and more accurate diagnoses, improve early management strategies, and ultimately increase the rates of successful preservation of the affected eyes.

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